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Disruptive Technologies Supporting Labour Market Decision Making

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<p>Abstract</p> <p>This document is framed in “WP5 Deployment and validation cycle”. It is written after the second version of the My Labour Market platform has been designed, developed and evaluated. It’s also included a comparative analysis with previous version of the platform and a set of conclusions from technical perspective about the results obtained during the piloting. This report in delivered in parallel with D5.3 which is showing the sociological assessment of the piloting results. Further explanations about the functionalities of the platform shall be found in the reports delivered under WP4 as D4.7.</p>	
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Statement of originality

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1. INTRODUCTION.

This report is showing the results of the last piloting with real users of Mylabourmarket.com (from now on MLM) developed by the Hecat partnership. It's based on data collected by Tecnalia team during the fieldwork at the two piloting sites in Slovenia – the public employment service (PES) offices in Ljubljana and Ptuj. In parallel, complements *D5.3 Report on collected data during pilot including benchmarking – sociological report*, developed by RUC partner.

MLM is built for the Slovenian labour market and PES through a collaborative effort across several disciplines (sociology, labour market research, computer science, social work, ICT), as well as national borders (Ireland, Slovenia, Spain, Denmark, France, Switzerland). The outcome is one tool but in fact several rather heterogenous functionalities. Meanwhile, all of the functionalities are based on the idea of letting the unemployed see her own personal labour market to support her in finding her way into the labour market.

The iterative process defined to achieve, in an agile way, a refined version of the MLM web tool ends up with this report (in addition with Del 5.3). In total, there's been three stages where the feedback from end-user has been collected:

Illustration 1. User's feedback has been gathered 3 times.

Between each stage, Tecnalia has implemented the improvements identified by the end users and the HECAT partners to the MLM web tool. In this process, JSI partner has also contributed to the platform evolution providing data and algorithm computation. The full representation of this iterative process it's described in Annex 1.

The conclusions of this report, including the ones coming from Del 5.3, are providing valuable insights for further evolution of the tool and the concepts around.

1.1. Deliverable content structure

This document is structured as follows:

- Chapter 2 explains how HECAT partnership managed to get to the last version of the MLM web tool, as it was a project stage quite intense.
- Chapter 3 focuses on a comparison between the two versions of the platform, showing the evolution of the functionalities.
- Chapter 4 shows the results of the assessment of the platform during the piloting from a technical point of view.
- Chapter 5 presents the main conclusions obtained.

2. MLM version 2

It's important to highlight in this chapter how the whole Hecat partnership managed to work closely and delivered the efforts for getting a new version of the MLM web tool. The results obtained from the piloting of MLM1 . (Sept 2022, described in Del 5.3) and the ambitions of the full partnership to get a better tool based on the user needs and behaviour, lead the partnership to define a working method for the next iteration of the web tool. The methodology was based on creating working groups (WG) where different project partners, contributed with their knowledge, experiences and opinions. Each working group was in charge of reviewing, assessing and evolving the core functionalities or sections. As a reminder, core sections in MLM1 were:

1. See the Labour Market – Basic and Advance Labour Market (statistical charts)
2. Job Progression Routes (a web form proposing new occupations attending to users input data)
3. Job Quality (the first version of the methodology for assessing the quality of a job attending to users' preferences)
4. Landing Page (important section which should capture the interest of users)

Then, these topics were grouped in the following working groups, dealing with that specific functionality below mentioned.

- WG1: Landing page, Basic Labour Market charts and Job Quality.
- WG2: Advanced Labour Market charts and PEX (Probability of existing unemployment).
- WG3: Job progression routes.

Each WG took a leader for ensuring an agenda and getting a consensual agreement; several partners took part in each WG and Tecnalía's and JSI's teams, as responsible for developing the new version, attended all meetings in order to advice and manage about the technical developments. Finally, it took three to four different meetings per each WG to reach an agreement about the new design and functionalities that were going to be built into the MLM v2. This work took from October '22 to January '23.

The result achieved, version 2 of the My Labour Market Platform, is a compendium of reorientation in design, offering more interaction and visualisation capabilities, as well as modifications to the algorithms.

But it is important to emphasize that throughout this process some of the premises that were established at the beginning of the project have been maintained and encouraged:

- **Speculative Design approach**¹ i.e., Design for the most probable and not for everything possible.
- The user must have **CONTROL** over navigation, over the choice of data to be displayed, over filtering...
- The user must be enabled to **LEARN**, mainly learning by doing, offering the necessary help or contextual information, enabling the learning of specific topics and concepts of the labour market.
- The user must have the possibility to **EXPLORE** the labour market information both in general and in detail, to identify new sectors.

¹ Dunne, A.; Raby, F. (2013). Speculative Everything. Design, Fiction, and Social Dreaming. Massachusetts: The MIT Press.

3. BENCHMARKING: My Labour Market Platform, from V1 to V2

In this chapter, the last two versions of the platform My Labour Market are compared. So, it can be understood the piloting results obtained in this new iteration. These two versions are the most complete ones, with some of the new functionalities developed under HECAT project showing an advanced status.

Further details about the refinement of the web tool may be found in the annex section, where it's possible to clearly see the incremental evolution of the platform.

My Labour Market V1	Sept 2022	http://v1.mylabourmarket.com/en/
My Labour Market v2	March 2023	http://www.mylabourmarket.com/en/

The objective of this chapter is to highlight most important changes that come from the work developed in the Working Groups, not to make an exhaustive description of each of them, as this information is available in the deliverables D4.7 User training manual and technical protocol v.1 and v.2.1.

Then, the description of the evolution of main functionalities are structured in this way for the following subsections:

- Landing Page
- Functionalities
- Interaction model
- Gamification

3.1. LANDING PAGE

The landing page has suffered a great change. his evolution has been conceived to better capture the user's interest in a quick way, trying to increase the impact of the contents in users' first visit to the web. Design has gone from a mainly explanatory design to a less overloaded design, being now lighter and reducing the space taken by the claim message.

Functionalities from previous version are almost the same but the designed and visual appearance has evolved much.

- "Main Menu", located at the top right, appearing collapsed to be easily recognisable by the users (under what it's called a "hamburger" menu, quite frequent in mobile apps), not taking up much space on the screen.

- "Teaser". This functionality has been agreed to be named in that way as it pretends to advance some figures about the labour market. It's the first opportunity to call for the user's curiosity so he/she may start interacting with data.
- And lastly, they've been included three "Calls to action" links to the main functionalities which are supposed to be covering the needs of the users when accessing the MLM web.

Now, the landing page is better oriented and designed to facilitate and speed up the user's understanding of the MLM.

Illustration 3. Landing Page evolution.

Illustration 2. Landing Page in My labour Market Platform V2, call to action.

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3.2. FUNCTIONALITIES

In this section the changes and new developments of the functionalities of the MLM web tool are introduced. Below is shown the MLM web map, where the changes between both versions can be observed.

Illustration 4. Information access in My labour Market Platform V1.

Illustration 5. Information access in My labour Market Platform V2.

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It can be seen that the new structure is lighter, only 3 levels for browsing web pages in comparison with the 4 levels defined in previous version. Green boxes just mean functions limited to registered users.

Also, most of the functions which remains the same are the ones that can be seen as *de-facto standard* for a web site: main menu, contact us, login, registration, privacy statement, etc.

The main changes are as follows:

- Naming of the functionalities. Trying to make them much more intuitive and easily understandable for the end users.
- Clustering of some sections, especially those corresponding to the graphs to look into the different metrics about the Labour Market.

And the final results that can be met in the MLM2 are as follows.

Along the 1st piloting one of the results was that users were not much interested in statistics or historical data. Then, it was agreed in the Working Groups to reduce the amount of statistical data charts. The option to “See the Labour Market” is reduced from 12 different charts to 6, removing the need to talk about basic or advanced metrics.

MLM1 Labelling	MLM2 Labelling
See the Labour Market: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Basic Labour Market <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Employed ○ Unemployed ○ Vacancies ○ New entrants per annum by economic sector ○ Average income ○ New entrants per annum by occupation ○ Average duration of unemployment • Advance Labour Market <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Employment stability ○ Rate of turnover of employees in existing jobs per annum ○ Net jobs created/destroyed per annum ○ Net people entering or leaving the employment ○ Estimated probability of entering employment from unemployment 	Explore Your Labour Market Trends: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Employed people • Compare Incomes • Average time unemployed • Compare duration of Unemployment • Career Stability • Labour Market liquidity
Job Progression Routes	Career Opportunities Tool
Job Quality	Bespoke Vacancies

And the specific charts under Basic/Advanced Labour Market pages, has turned into these new naming.

MLM1 Labelling	MLM2 Labelling
Employed Stability	Career Stability
Liquidity concept splitted on 3 plots: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rate of turnover of employees in existing jobs per annum • Net jobs created/destroyed per annum • Net people entering or leaving the employment 	Labour Market Liquidity
Estimated probability of entering employment from unemployment	Average time unemployed
Average Income	Compare Incomes
Average Duration of Unemployment	Compare Duration of Unemployment

The most far-reaching changes within the main functionalities have been those set out at “Bespoke Vacancies”, “Career Opportunities Tool” and “Average Time Unemployed”, which are detailed now in below sections.

3.2.1. Bespoke Vacancies

This is one of the most changed pieces of information, in terms of display and user interaction. In MLM1, the information on "vacancies" was a statistical data depending on the selected occupation. It was possible to see its evolution over time. As regarding its location, it was in the section "See the labour market" - "Basic Labour Market".

Illustration 6. Vacancies information, in section "See the labour market" - "Basic Labour Market", in My labour Market Platform V1.

Now, in version 2 of the platform, the information about "Vacancies" takes on an entity of its own and becomes a section in the main navigation menu "Bespoke Vacancies".

It was understood by the WG1 that Job Quality in MLM1 feature was also able to provide vacancies, then it was identified the possibility to talk about Bespoke Vacancies, empowered by the notion of "quality" bespoke to user preferences about what he/she considers about quality, when selecting the different filters available. So, in this advanced visualization, the available vacancies have been previously jointly analyzed taking into account the quality factors important to users.

In a first approach to this section by the end-user, the information displayed varies according to the parameters chosen by the end-user: "Localisation", "Occupation" and "Wished working time".

This is a general overview of the new section. In the following the differentiated characteristics will be detailed.

BESPOKE VACANCIES MAP

Here you have the chance to see what are the quality of the current job offer in Slovenia.

Please, fill in the following data and choose what are the main aspects for you for talking about the quality of a job. And the algorithm will show you the level of quality regarding the aspects you selected.

FILL AND CHOOSE

Current location: Professional Occupation: User wishes for working time:

(Specify your current or nearest location.)

What are the most important aspects for your job?

HERE YOU CAN NARROW YOUR SEARCH

Autonomy and control over working tasks
E.g. ability to choose your methods or speed of work and influence decisions important for your work. (i)

Meaningful work
E.g. having a job that gives you the feeling of work well done or of doing useful work. (i)

Training opportunities at work
Jobs including training opportunities. (i)

Career advancement
Good prospects for career advancement. (i)

Limited physical risks
Removes job offers carrying high physical risks (e.g. painful positions, lifting or moving heavy loads or people) from search results. (i)

Limited psycho-social risks
Removes job offers carrying high psycho-social risks (e.g. worrying about work when you were not working) from search results. (i)

Standard working time
No night work or week-end work. (i)

Flexible working time
Removes job offers where you may not adapt your working time to your needs. (i)

Worker representation
E.g. Trade union representative at the workplace. (i)

📍 High quality
 📍 Medium quality
 📍 Low quality

Accounting associate professionals

Accountants

If you are interested, [here you can find additional information](#) on how were computed the indicators displayed in this 'BESPOKE VACANCIES' section. Recommended only for advanced users.

Illustration 7. Overview of the “Bespoke vacancies” section, in My labour Market Platform V2.

The result is as follows. The information is shown georeferenced on a map, where the existing vacancies are indicated. The end user can move freely around the map. Each of the vacancies are shown on the map allowing the user to select them one at a time. At that moment a pop-up appears with information related to that specific vacancy: the name of the company, the type of contract, salary data and the link to the web page where it's published the vacancy.

Illustration 8. Specific details of a vacancy, in “Bespoke Vacancies” section, in My labour Market Platform V2.

At the bottom of the map, the vacancy data is displayed in table format.

POSITION TITLE	LOCATION	HOURS PER WEEK	PAY AND OTHER REWARDS	JOB WORKING TIME	DISTANCE TO WORK	AVERAGE EARNINGS
RAČUNOVODJA - M/Ž	LJUBLJANA	40	similar	Full-time	near location	1560.0€
SAMOSTOJNI STROKOVNI DELAVEC VII/2 (I) V FINANČNO-RAČUNOVODSKI SLUŽBI - M/Ž	LJUBLJANA	40	similar	Full-time	near location	1560.0€
RAČUNOVODJA VI (J018027) - M/Ž	LJUBLJANA	40	similar	Full-time	near location	1560.0€
STROKOVNI SODELAVEC V SEKTORJU ZA FINANCE IN RAČUNOVODSTVO (PODROČJE FINANC, KONTROLINGA IN RAČUNOVODSTVA) - M/Ž	LJUBLJANA	40	similar	Full-time	near location	1560.0€
RAČUNOVODJA - M/Ž	LJUBLJANA	40	similar	Full-time	near location	1560.0€
VODJA SLUŽBE V SLUŽBI ZA RAČUNOVODSTVO - M/Ž	LJUBLJANA	40	similar	Full-time	near location	1560.0€
RAČUNOVODJA VII/2 - M/Ž	LJUBLJANA	40	similar	Full-time	near location	1560.0€
J017090 RAČUNOVODJA VII/1 - M/Ž	LJUBLJANA	40	similar	Full-time	near location	1560.0€
SAMOSTOJNI RAČUNOVODJA - M/Ž	LJUBLJANA	40	similar	Full-time	near location	1560.0€
REVIZOR ZAČETNIK - M/Ž	LJUBLJANA	40	similar	Full-time	near location	1560.0€
RAČUNOVODJA - M/Ž	LJUBLJANA	40	similar	Full-time	near location	1560.0€
RAČUNOVODJA 67%, RAČUNALNIKAR 33% - M/Ž	LJUBLJANA	40	similar	Full-time	near location	1560.0€

Illustration 9. Vacancy information in table format, in “Bespoke Vacancies” section, in My labour Market Platform V2.

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A colour code is also used on the map to specify the quality of the vacancies according to the search criteria.

Illustration 10. Classification of vacancies according to their quality in “Bespoke Vacancies” section, in My labour Market Platform V2.

In the case that an advanced user wants to go deeper about how were computed the indicators displayed in this "Bespoke Vacancies" section there is a link to this information:

If you are interested, [here you can find additional information](#) on how were computed the indicators displayed in this "BESPOKE VACANCIES" section. Recommended only for advanced users.

Illustration 11. Additional information about how the indicators were computed, in “Bespoke Vacancies” section, in My labour Market Platform V2.

3.2.2. Career Opportunities Tool

This section allows the user to obtain as a result the best rated occupations according to the selected preferences. So the user can interact with data about his or her current real situation, or test with desirable data, in order to evaluate new alternatives or broaden horizons. It should be taken into account that the results obtained are estimations and are based on the own Slovenian companies' forecasts for short term hiring.

This section is the equivalent of "Job Progression Routes" in version 1 of the platform, but with some differences.

First of all, the amount of information requested from the user has been reduced, removing “career progression wishes” and “wished location” boxes, because the way information is represented in actual version already allows to move around different locations.

Secondly, the way in which the results are displayed has changed, as in version 1 the information was only shown in a table, but in this new version the information is combined in a map, and it's also displayed a pop-up for each anchor on the map and results are put together in a table. And the resulting occupations are grouped as "Closer to your preferences" or "Slightly more distant from your preferences".

Illustration 12. New visualisation of the results in "Career opportunities tool" section, in My labour Market Platform V2.

3.2.3. Average time unemployed

Information regarding the time a user might need to get out of unemployment is provided as a result in a different way. In version 1 of the platform (located under "See the labour market -> Advance information") this information was only available for "Counsellor" user profiles, i.e. for labour market experts, because it could be sensitive information for the job seeker.

However, in version 2 of the platform (located in "Explore your labour market trends"), it was decided in the Working Group to offer this information openly to all users, so that they can be the ones to value it. To this end, the information requested from the user has been modified.

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Estimated probability of entering employment from unemployment

Historical data on the average time people remain unemployed customised by occupation and location. Source: Public Employment Services of Slovenia (PES).

City: Ljubljana | Disability: Categorized Adolescent (ZiOPP 1878) | Gender: male | Employment plan status: Employment plan in preparation

Occupation code: Agronomist for agriculture | Reason for entering pes: Application according to APZ - without employment | Employment plan ready: Employment plan not required | Age: 48

Months of work experience: 28

Illustration 13. Required information in “Estimated probability of entering employment from unemployment”, in “see the labour market -> advance labour market” section, in My labour Market Platform V1.

Employed people | Compare Incomes | **Average time unemployed** | Compare duration of Unemployment

Career Stability | Labour Market liquidity

Average time unemployed

Historical data on the average time people remain unemployed customised by occupation and location. Source: Public Employment Services of Slovenia (PES).

Education direction: Agriculture not elsewhere classified | Reason for termination your last job: Expiration of a fixed-term employment relationship | Gender: male

Occupation code: Agricultural, forestry and fishery labourers | Education level: Second cycle of higher and similar education/Second cyc

Employment plan ready: Employment plan not required | Unemployment benefits: No | Social support benefits: No

Date of pes entry: 2022-10-19 | Age: 42 | Months work experience: 48 | City: Ljubljana

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Illustration 14. Required information in “Average time unemployed “ metric, in “Explore your labour market trends” section, in My labour Market Platform V2.

And the way in which the results are displayed has been simplified, while maintaining the combination of graphs and explanatory text, which is programmed automatically to be presented attending to the numerical results.

Now are compared previous version in illustration 15 versus the next one.

Illustration 15. Results visualization of “Estimated probability of entering employment from unemployment”, in “see the labour market -> advance labour market” section, in My labour Market Platform V1.

In this reviewed version, it’s shown how the automatic explanatory text is improved. On horizontal axis, it’s the number of days for finding a job, and Z variable (red-dotted line) shows the interval of days where the probability of finding a job is 90%.

Illustration 16. Results in “Average time unemployed “ metric, in “Explore your labour market trends” section, in My labour Market Platform V2

3.3. VISUALIZATION

Throughout the development of the second version of the platform, a simpler interaction has been designed and, in some respects, closer to the "standards" to which users are used to regarding different websites and applications.

Regarding the visualisation of information, version 1 of the platform was basically focused on statistical tables and graphs. In version 2, the visualisation aspects and graphical resources have been reinforced. More contents as maps, pop-ups, tables, graphs and colour coding have been combined in order to show the information in a way that is easier for the end user to understand, locate and interact with.

It is also necessary to remark that, as the project has had a continuous development, data availability (provided from WP3) has improved, and new data has been possible to show. For example, obtaining the localization of some datasets which has enabled a breakthrough in being able to use maps as a graphic resource for displaying information.

Despite the changes, the interaction structure of the data graphics was decided to keep the same, with minor modifications to the design, lightening the visual load on the screen.

Illustration 17. Interaction structure for graphs , in My labour Market Platform V1.

Illustration 18. Interaction structure for graphs , in My labour Market Platform V2.

In these sections, user interaction remains located at the same points, which have been numbered in the diagrams above and explained here in detail.

1. At the heading of the page appears the name of the indicator and a brief description.
2. Below, there are some filters (drop down lists), where the user can select the variable defined, being Occupations, Sectors or Years... When lists are large, it's activated a character search facility.

Below the chart, users have two more functionalities:

3. "Graph info" button, where users can have further information about the chart they're at.
4. Link for requesting expert advice.
5. Access to Highcharts² functionalities for downloading data or full-screen view.

² <https://www.highcharts.com/demo>

Now there are a series of modifications and examples made related to the information visualization on the platform.

3.3.1. Hamburger menu

In order to get a better design, the lateral navigation menu has been replaced by the well-known hamburger menu, quite common object in many mobile and web applications. In this way, it's achieved a cleaner designed page which allows the user pays attention on main contents.

Illustration 19. Main menu evolution.

Illustration 20. Extended main navigation menu in My labour Market Platform V2.

Navigation in version 1 was via a static top menu at the top of the screen. In the case of the "See the Labour Market" section, which was divided into 2 sub-sections, each with several graphs to display, a fixed vertical menu was used on the left side of the page.

In version 2, the menu is collapsed in the upper right part of the image, using the "Hamburger menu" resource. In this way, the visual load on the screen is reduced, making the content clearer and lighter.

The only case where a section has other subsections is "Explore your Labour Market Trends", Where it has been decided to put some buttons at the top of the section (a kind of menu) where the user can choose the graph to visualise, keeping the perception that the user is still in the same section. Graphically it is used a very light way of visualising.

Illustration 21. Buttons for different graphs, in My labour Market Platform V2.

Regarding this change, it's to be noted that during the re-designing of the page it was technically assessed the possibility to show at one time all the data charts, making possible users will have to choose only once the search criteria and then all charts will be charged in the page providing the results. Finally, it was refused this option as it was verified the high time response the system took to show the results which provoked a lack of useability.

3.3.2. Comparison on the same graph

Working Groups opted for a more reduced but useful and more understandable information for users. A combination of simple graphical representations has been chosen, generally with linear diagrams, but allowing **comparisons between different occupations**, helping end users to better understand the data.

The origin of this idea is the feedback obtained from user feedback regarding the possibility to make comparisons within the same graph, i.e. to be able to see the value represented, but for more than one occupation at the same time.

Illustration 22. “Employed people” metric screenshot, in My labour Market Platform V2. Only data available from 2020 on.

But being able to make these comparisons between occupations on the same graph is not possible for cases where more complex metrics are represented and therefore more advanced graphical resources need to be used.

The possibility of comparison, showing all the information from different occupations, would greatly increase the difficulty of interpretation of the information for users. This is clearly seen in the metrics “Career Stability” and “Labour Market Liquidity”.

Illustration 23. “Labour market liquidity” metric screenshot, in My labour Market Platform V2.

The above illustration corresponds to the metric "Labour Market Liquidity", which is a measure of how easy it is to find a job in a particular occupation by looking at the turnover of jobs. Some jobs are scarce and hard to find, illiquid, and other jobs are frequently available, liquid.

The idea is that the user can see the liquidity value for a given occupation ("Liquidity" black line) and compare it with the average liquidity across all occupations ("Overall mean" broken line) and see where it falls within the range of maximum and minimum liquidity values for all occupations (blue shading area).

In this case, if the detailed information from more than one occupation were to be entered in the same graph, it would be much more difficult to represent the information and to understand it.

3.3.3. Shortening of time series

Although it has been possible to obtain data for some of the metrics for long time series, users reported in the first piloting stage they didn't have much interest on the past, so the WG decided to show data from the very recent years.

Illustration 24. Example of long time series display in My labour Market Platform VI.

3.5. GAMIFICATION

Gamification strategy was conceived as a tool for strengthen user engagement with the new concepts MLM is proposing. By “Engagement” shall be understood the end-users’ motivation to keep a continuous interaction with MLM web tool just for the value it provides to them.

The full set of gamification techniques (fully described in the report D4.7 User training manual and technical protocols v.1) finally implemented to MLM1 were:

1. **Sense of progress**
2. **Tip of the day**
3. **Expert advice**
4. **Advanced user profile**
5. **Fostering learn, users’ feedback**
6. **Meet the tool, kind of tutorial**

The logic behind these functions was:

Users who most access and interact with the My Labour Market become advanced user and are rewarded with a prize. This prize is the possibility to get expert advice about understanding the labour market within their interest while they are interacting with MLM web tool.

Then, the “force for engagement” that shall be pulling users to MLM is coming from the supporting role of some mentors that help users to find answers.

In the first piloting stage, it was observed users most valued the possibility to be in contact with a labour market expert who may provide them with some advice. Then, it was decided to remove others gamification techniques with less impact in the user engagement so the platform may earn simplicity, and then, useability. Those gamification features removed were “Sense of progress” and “Tip of the day”. Then, **MLM2 gamification is based on these features:**

1. **Expert advice**
2. **Fostering learn, users’ feedback sending**
3. **Meet the tool, kind of tutorial**

Then, gamification has been piloted and verified with the users focusing on the Expert Advice “reward” they may get if they get registered within the web. Registration process has kept the same level of safety, aligned with GDPR, ensuring no personal data is collected. Registration is required to make available the communication between end-user and the labour market expert.

MLM1 Gamification features	MLM2 Gamification features
<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Sense of progress2. Tip of the day3. Expert advice4. Advanced user profile5. Fostering learn, users' feedback6. Meet the tool, kind of tutorial	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Expert advice2. Fostering learn, users' feedback3. Meet the tool, kind of tutorial

4. PILOTING MLM v2

The piloting Tecnia carried out was designed from a technical perspective, following methodologies for evaluating the useability of the new version of MLM (MLM2).

This piloting phase was held in the field in collaboration with RUC team, as WP leader, and Tecnia was in charge of assessing the Gamification features developed and also provided the System Useability Scale (SUS) evaluation. Both partners run their own methodology and interviewed end-users, one after each other. The piloting took place along the week of March 13th, 2023, in Ljubljana and Ptuj.

4.1. METHODOLOGY

In order to evaluate the user experience during the piloting of the MLM2 it's been deployed the methodology Tecnia used to implement, combining both quantitative and qualitative metrics.

First, they're defined some tasks users have to perform by themselves over the MLM web tool. Evaluator observes how user interacts with the tool so it can be concluded how well users do by themselves with the application. Afterwards, it's put in place the SUS questionnaire (a quantitative scoring scale, later explained) which is broadly accepted when evaluating user acceptance of information systems.

Additionally, a set of final questions were proposed to end users in order to get more feedback from them about the overall concept of the My Labour Market tool.

Then, all conclusions will be built from those sources:

1. The evaluation about how the user have performed the tasks.
2. The feedback provided in that last set of questions.
3. The scoring from the SUS survey.

Illustration 25. Piloting process.

4.1.1. User profile

The ideal situation for testing this type of applications is to cover the widest possible spectrum of user typologies, according to different levels of knowledge of technologies, different degrees of interaction with it, different educational levels, different work situations, etc.

This data about the users who finally took part in the piloting is included in the Annex chapter. The process to identify and collect these users were led by the local project partner ESS.

4.1.2. Piloting Tasks

These tasks were designed by Tecnalía's team, and the users had access to the questionnaires at the beginning of the testing. The format of each questionnaire was as follows:

- A brief introduction explaining the context of the test.
- The tasks to be performed, each with a description
- A set of final questions.

During the test process, the evaluators have tried to act as little as possible with the user in order not to influence him/her. Of course, if the user gets stuck and cannot continue with the process, evaluators tried to find the best way for him/her to continue, giving as few indications as possible.

The user is asked to share out loud his thoughts, his doubts, as this feedback is very useful.

The material available once the test is over is:

- The notes taken by the evaluators of the comments made by the user during the test.
- The questionnaires, with its different sections, answered in writing by the users.

For each of these tasks there is a description, specific questions and a section to assess the difficulty of the task. They are also asked to explain in writing how they have carried out the task, the different steps.

These are the specific tasks that were designed for the piloting with unemployed end users.

Task 1	<i>"The first task is to get in touch with the tool, so please, open the website (http://www.mylabourmarket.com/) and take some time to browse through it and try to get to know what the tool offers and how to interact with it. <u>Please do not go through the registration process now, it will be done later.</u>"</i>
Task 2	<i>"Now let's go one step further in the tool!! Now, register yourself on the tool and log in to gain access to all services provided."</i>
Task 3	<i>"According to the possibilities that the tool offers to you at the moment, try to find out what are the open vacancies available for your occupation (or the one that you prefer) in your municipality. Once you have tried it, write your doubts or questions on this section on the platform, so that they can be answered by an expert in the job market."</i>
Task 4	<i>"As in the previous task you shared a question or doubt, check your workspace to see if you got an answer from the labour market expert.."</i>

These were the ones designed for the testing process, for a user profile "Counsellor".

Task 1	<i>"The first thing you are going to do is open the website (http://www.mylabourmarket.com/) and take some time to browse through it and try to get to know what the tool offers and how to interact with it. <u>Please do not go through the registration process now, it will be done later.</u>"</i>
Task 2	<i>"Now, register yourself on the tool and log in to gain access to all services provided."</i>
Task 3	<i>"As an expert in labour marking, you are entitled to respond to questions or doubts raised by users of the tool in an area that has been set up as "doubts or questions". Go to your personal area and check if there is any doubt raised by the user _____. If so, try to send him/her a reply."</i>

The results of this first test are described in chapter [4.2. Overall results](#).

4.1.3. Final questions

Once users had carried out all the tasks described in the previous chapter, they are requested to answer some general questions about the direct use of the tool and the trust it generates.

There are two questions for the "Job Seeker" profile and two questions for the "Counsellor" profile. They should rate their level of trust or agreement.

Questions for "Job seeker" Profile:

1. Does this advice service motivate you to explore deeper into the platform?
2. Would you access the MLM platform more frequently now that you know you have this free, personalised advice service?
3. How would you rate the usefulness of having this personalised support service?

Questions for "Counsellor" profile:

1. I believe that "My Labour Market" tool will be useful for me to complement the tools I already have available to offer the counselling service.
2. I consider appropriate and useful to be able to give my expert support through the online service offered by this platform.

The results of this test are described in chapter 2.2. Overall results.

4.1.4. SUS scale

The **System Usability Scale (SUS)**³ questionnaire was developed in 1986 as part of the introduction of usability engineering to office systems by Digital Equipment Co. Ltd. Its purpose is to provide a test that is simple to complete (minimum number of questions), easy to score and allows cross-comparisons between products (Information Systems in this case). It is a questionnaire that is broad accepted in the industry and, after years of application, it has proven to be simple and reliable.

The SUS is based on 10 standard sentences the user has to score his/her agreement degree:

1. **I think that I would like to use this tool frequently.**
2. **I found the tool unnecessarily complex.**
3. **I thought the tool was easy to use.**
4. **I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this tool.**
5. **I found the various functions in this tool were well integrated.**
6. **I thought there was too much inconsistency in this tool.**
7. **I would imagine that most people would learn to use this tool very quickly.**
8. **I found the tool very difficult to use.**
9. **I felt very confident using the system tool.**
10. **I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this tool.**

And these are the options for answering them, according to the level of agreement on the previous questions:

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Agree
- Strongly agree

The SUS scale is generally used after a user has had the opportunity to interact with a system, but before any reporting or discussion takes place. Users are asked to immediately complete their response to each item, rather than thinking long and hard about it. In this case the SUS questionnaire has been completed by the users after the end of the piloting session.

Thus, the SUS questionnaire results in a rating of the Information System on a scale from 0 to 100 (and from A+ to F-) where, according to numerous studies, **the average and therefore minimum score to ensure that a system is usable is 68 out of 100 or C-value.**

³ <https://www.nngroup.com/videos/system-usability-scale/>

This is the table with the scales of the SUS questionnaires, C is the minimum score to achieve.

A+	A	A-	B+	B	B-	C+	C	C-	D	F	F-
90	82	80	78	75	73	72	68	63	55	50	44

In the following section all the results are explained.

4.2. OVERALL RESULTS

Now the results from the tasks, the answers provided by the users and the SUS scoring are detailed and analysed.

It's also to be commented about the final user involvement Hecat partners got. As in many processes like this one, users' involvement is a bit tricky. Once they are called as volunteers, nobody can have high expectations about their commitment to stay along the full process and perform all steps the experts think about. Then, not all users took part in the whole process by different circumstances. Finally, SUS survey was done by 14 users, the gamification evaluation and the final questions form were completed by 5 users. (See "[Appendix 2. Characteristics of interviewed in piloting of MLM 2, March 2023](#)").

4.2.1. Piloting Tasks

In general, all users did all tasks by themselves without any major issues and within a normal timeframe.

When they were requested to raise a question/doubt to be sent and answered by an expert on the labour market, all of them did without any problem.

Regarding the task about accessing the "My Workspace" section, in order to get the answer provided by the labour market expert, most users did so right **although only one** answered that he found it difficult to interact with it.

And lastly, it was asked to the users about how much time they would be willing to wait for getting the expert advice and the general response was 3 days as much.

Regarding the "My Workspace" section, users proposed some interesting improvements:

- To be displayed the date when the information request and expert advice are raised.
- To send by e-mail a notification when the answer is already available.

Now are detailed some relevant and explicit quotes given by the users:

- *"I would add login with email or even SI-PASS / EU-PASS."* (User 1)
- *"The answer should come in a reasonable time."* (User 1)

- *“The only thing I would change is if it were possible to use your gmail to register, so that could also be used as the user name.” (User 2)*
- *“If there were a possibility to use your gmail to register, it would also help to get notifications when you get your answer, so you don’t have to look on the site every day.” (User 2)*
- *“A notification would be helpful. I could easily and gladly login with an email account.” (User 4)*

Moreover, it’s important to highlight user’s perception about the sharing of personal data. It should be noted that none of the users would mind sharing their email address for the registration process. Actually, two of the users asked for it, arguing that it is something they are totally used to. Another user said he would give his email, but only when the platform has gone through development stage. And other user, who were better digital skilled, even proposed the use of SI-PASS for registration (a national authentication platform in Slovenia).

Then, from the tasks evaluation it can be highlighted that:

- 1. In relation to the tasks carried out by users, their user experience was quite good.**
- 2. Expert advice service from labour market experts is positively valued among users.**
- 3. Users have fully internalised sharing an email address, and even find it useful for additional services such as notifications.**

4.2.2. Final questions

This is a summary of the results obtained from these last activities about the tasks.

Those are **the results for “Job seeker profile”**:

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
1. Does this advice service motivate you to explore deeper into the platform?			✓ ✓	✓ ✓	✓

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
2. Would you access the MLM platform more frequently now that you know you have this free, personalised advice service?					

	Very Low	Low	High	Very High
3. Usefulness of having this personalised support service				

And these are some relevant and explicit quotes users shared about the experience.

Does this advice service motivate you to explore deeper into the platform?

- *“It’s an interesting tool to use but I don’t think I would use it that often”. (User 2)*
- *“Yes, definitely, because any lack of understanding can be easily resolved through the expert advice given”. (User 4)*

Would you access the MLM platform more frequently now that you know you have this free, personalised advice service?

- *“I find it more useful than the pages currently available. (User 1)*
- *“It’s useful to learn about the job you’re interested in but for finding a job I would say that there are better ways.” (User 2)*
- *“Yes, because I can receive more personalized data on the topics I’m interested in”. (User 4)*

How would you rate the usefulness of having this personalised support service?

- *“I believe it is useful to ask the questions if the user is puzzled by something, but the answer should come in reasonable time” (User 2)*
- *“As long as the reaction time of the expert is quick (max 3 days, but faster if possible, depending on the type of question and the urgency of it) then the feature is fantastic”. (User 4)*
- *“Nice to get an answer” (User 5)*

Other comments:

- *“In general, I find the web useful but some parts no, as Stability and Liquidity data” (User 3)*

So, to summarise, it can be highlighted at qualitative level that:

- 4. The tool is useful to find information about what you are interested in.**
- 5. It can be highlighted that, on the job seekers’ side, there is a positive feeling about using the tool more frequently once they have experienced the personalised advice service, as long as they get the answers to their questions within a reasonable period of time.**
- 6. There were collected 13 to 15 answers which are positive (qualitatively). Only were classified as neutral 2 responses (Neither agree nor disagree).**

4.2.3. SUS scale

These are the results for the “Job seeker” profile. In this case, it was possible to collect data from 14 users involved in the piloting who interacted with the whole set of functionalities of MLM web tool. For getting these figures, it’s been used an on-line calculator⁴ which runs the whole algorithm involved in the SUS method and provides the results for each form automatically.

User	SUS	Scale
User1	85	A
User 2	50	F
User 3	90	A+
User 4	75	B
User 5	42,5	F-
User 6	55	D
User 7	72,5	C+
User 8	80	A-

⁴ [SUS calculator](#)

User 9	90	A+
User 10	87,5	A
User 11	90	A+
User 12	80	A-
User 13	82,5	A
User 14	92,5	A+
Average	76,60	B

Being C the minimum score to achieve:

A+	A	A-	B+	B	B-	C+	C	C-	D	F	F-
90	82	80	78	75	73	72	68	63	55	50	44

Attending to these results it can be concluded that:

- 7. The intention to use this tool frequently is high, with most of users considering it easy to use, without the need for technical support. With a high level of confidence about it and not being necessary to learn things before to be able to use it.**
- 8. Regarding all answers collected from users in the SUS questionnaire, grouping them as positive or negative, it can be observed there are a 75.71% of positive responses and a 12.14% as negative. The rest up to 100% is evaluated by users as neutral responses.**

5. CONCLUSIONS

Let's bring back again all takeaways from the users:

1. **In relation to the tasks carried out by users, their user experience was quite good.**
2. **Expert advice service from labour market experts is positively valued among users.**
3. **Users have fully internalised sharing an email address, and even find it useful for additional services such as notifications.**
4. **The tool is useful to find information about what you are interested in.**
5. **It can be highlighted that, on the job seekers' side, there is a positive feeling about using the tool more frequently once they have experienced the personalised advice service, as long as they get the answers to their questions within a reasonable period of time.**
6. **There were collected 13 to 15 answers which are positive (qualitatively). Only were classified as neutral 2 responses (Neither agree nor disagree).**
7. **The intention to use this tool frequently is high, with most of users considering it easy to use, without the need for technical support. With a high level of confidence about it and not being necessary to learn things before to be able to use it.**
8. **In parallel to SUS methodology, it can be also seen that there are 75.71% of answers being positive against a 12.14% as negative.**

From a technical point of view, which is, focusing on the user experience results and attending to the UCD principles⁵, it may be concluded that **the MLM platform largely fulfils user's requirements and needs**. Users were able to carry out all the tasks in a more than reasonable way, without facing remarkable issues about how to interact with the different functionalities of the tool.

Regarding the specific results about the expert advice "service", related to the gamification features proposed, there's no doubt **users appreciated having the chance to appeal for that service**⁶ once they find some doubts about the information they're accessing.

On the other hand, there's also a chance to compare the **results coming from the SUS method**, which provides a quantitative assessment that's also important to take into account. During the testing phase developed under WP4 (done in July 2022) it was also applied a SUS survey for

⁵ User-Centered Design Principles: (1) A clear understanding of user and task requirements; (3) Incorporating user feedback to define requirements and design. (4) Early and active involvement of the user to evaluate the design of the product.

⁶ This service has to be clearly differentiated from a mere technical service supporting users about technical bugs, breakdowns and outages.

that MLM version, which could be seen as v.0. All that work done is described in report *D4.5 Living-lab simulation, iterative process of review and update v.1.1*

Both results could be compared as it's the same method applied to different versions of the platform, so it could be concluded if the last changes applied actually made some benefits. But, in fact, they can't be completely compared because both assessments were not carried out with the same sample, the number of users finally involved in the testing were quite different and it influences much the average metric. The values obtained from these two SUS evaluation are included in the annex.

User Job Seeker	SUS	Scale	Sample size
MLM v.0	81	A-	7
MLM v.2	76,60	B	14

Finally, the following robust conclusion can be drawn as a general result of the work carried out:

Within the technical context of this report, the overall result obtained about usability of My Labour Market web platform is quite positive. From quantitative data, the SUS result is exceeding the threshold established by the method and from qualitative data, the feedback obtained from users as well can be taken as positive.

6. TOWARDS MLM V.3.

After the research carried out by Tecnalia they've been identified some clues or tips that might be taken into account for next developments of the MLM web tool regarding the aspects related with the user experience, gamification and also some additional technological aspects.

User Experience (UX)

- The interaction design framework (D4.1) proposed several end-user archetypes with different needs and expectations about the MLM tool: unemployed, employed, students, LTU and, lastly, even scientists. It's quite challenging to think about accomplishing with all those one's expectations. So, it may be good exercise to narrow the kind of users to think about when going for a new version or just think to define a deeper functionality based on the different profiles of a user. (In this sense, it hasn't to be confused with the "profiling issue" referenced on the sociological reports dealing with data from unemployed people.)
- On the other hand, MLM market tool has followed a responsive web design but finally, minor access has come from portable platforms. All the accesses have been coming from desktops and big screens so many of the format of the results provided by the tool must be optimised for mobiles. For example, the tables showing all the results of the vacancies in Bespoke Vacancies or Career opportunities are not going to be the best way to show the data under the little screens of mobiles/tablets.

Gamification

- It was concluded by gamification experts that the most engaging aspect of MLM tool was the data by itself. It's enough motivating for a user to access the tool which promises to provide relevant data that could help users get a better job regarding any aspect such as localization, economic sector, working time, wage, quality, etc. Then, any new version of MLM shall guarantee providing curated data, with enough quality, accuracy and trust for the users.

Technological

- All statistical data about a professional occupation has been found to be always referenced to the ESCO⁷ model (occupational classification) which is quite far away from the daily usage of people. It's been an issue well reported in some deliverables, which could be fixed with some technological developments as the implementation of semantic-base or natural language processing tools.
- In the time this project has reached the last stage, generative IA has strongly emerged, and it shall be recommendable to assess how this technology may contribute to the concept of MLM tool.

⁷ https://esco.ec.europa.eu/en/classification/occupation_main

APPENDICES

Appendix 1. Iterative process in MLM Platform

Here it's described the iterative process which has finally ended with the MLM v.2. First it was released a draft version of the tool, with a first approach of the main functionalities and its naming. Then, it was reached a minimum viable prototype (MVP) in June, with some functionalities better evolved and mature. First contact with real end-users in July '22 allowed to get good feedback which make possible the platform evolution to the first piloting (Sep '22). And for ending the process, a new released of MLM were produced and launched in March '23 to be piloted for the last stage.

Illustration 26. Evolution and versioning of MLM web tool.

Looking at the following diagram, it can be clearly understood the functional evolution of the platform since the draft version released in March 2022.

Illustration 27. Functional evolution of MLM web tool.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research & innovation programme under grant agreement No 870702

Appendix 2. Characteristics of interviewed in piloting of MLM 2, March 2023

Unemployed people:

Alias	Age	Sex	City	Educational background	Professional background	Duration of unemployment
Unemployed23	33	m	Ljubljana	None	Translator, Web developer, Operates 2 blogs atm (spiritual practices)	8 years
Unemployed24	54	m	Ljubljana	University degree in Philosophy and sociology of culture	Worked pro bono for several human organizations + digitalization of sources in an organisation	10 years
Unemployed25	51	f	Ljubljana		Retail	15 years
Unemployed26	27	f	Ptuj	High school	H	
Unemployed27	22	f	Ljubljana	Bachelor in translation, studying masters in translation	-	student
Unemployed28		m	Ljubljana	-	-	
Unemployed29	43	m	Ljubljana	Metallurgist, Metal engineer		5-6 years
Unemployed30	26	f	Ljubljana	Studies Sinology (without student status)	Bookstore, clothes shop (student work)	student
Unemployed31	53	f	Ptuj			
Unemployed32		f	Ljubljana		Sales and marketing	2 years

Counsellors:

Alias	Age	Sex	City	Educational background	Group of unemployed	Employment period
Counsellor2		m	Ljubljana	Philosopher		8,5 years
Counsellor4		f	Ptuj			
Counsellor8		f	Ljubljana			Since 2016
Counsellor9		f	Ptuj	Sociologist	Young people with disabilities	23-24 years
Counsellor10		f	Ljubljana			33 years

List of users who took part in the gamification assessment:

Alias	Age	Occupation	Education	Use of technology
Unemployed 28	40	unemployed	High school education, computer technician.	Advance use regarding technology
Unemployed27	22	Student	Bachelors in translation, studying for masters	Use it very often, every day. Mostly news and information for translation

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Unemployed29	43	Metallurgy engineering	Level VII. Metallurgy engineering graduate	Good use of it. Daily news.
Unemployed23	33	Translation, Web development , counselling	High school, some university	High level proficiency in terms of all forms of devices (PC, phone) as well as websites and Apps.
Unemployed24	54	Caregiver	Level 5.	Social networks. Facebook looking for jobs, my work

To be noted, these five are among the first list of users.

Appendix 3. SUS survey results for MLM 2 piloting , March 2023

Only 3 users rated the tool to be under the threshold of usability, which makes the average goes down. That represents a 21% of users considering the tool as of low usability.

User	SUS	Scale
User1	85	A
User 2	50	F
User 3	90	A+
User 4	75	B
User 5	42,5	F-
User 6	55	D
User 7	72,5	C+
User 8	80	A-
User 9	90	A+
User 10	87,5	A
User 11	90	A+
User 12	80	A-
User 13	82,5	A
User 14	92,5	A+
Average	76,60	B

Now, it's a detailed summary of all answers obtained to achieve the results from the SUS method.

Regarding “My Labour Market” tool ...	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
1. I think that I would like to use this tool frequently.		✓	✓✓	✓✓ ✓✓ ✓	✓✓✓ ✓✓ ✓
2. I found the tool unnecessarily complex.	✓✓✓ ✓	✓✓✓ ✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓	
3. I thought the tool was easy to use.		✓	✓	✓✓ ✓	✓✓✓ ✓✓ ✓✓
4. I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this tool.	✓✓✓ ✓✓✓ ✓✓✓ ✓	✓✓	✓	✓	
5. I found the various functions in this tool were well integrated.		✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓ ✓	✓✓✓ ✓✓
6. I thought there was too much inconsistency in this tool.	✓✓✓ ✓✓✓	✓	✓	✓✓ ✓✓ ✓	✓
7. I would imagine that most people would learn to use this tool very quickly.			✓✓✓	✓✓ ✓✓	✓✓✓ ✓✓ ✓

8. I found the tool very difficult to use.	✓✓✓ ✓✓✓ ✓	✓✓✓ ✓	✓✓	✓	
9. I felt very confident using the system tool.		✓	✓	✓✓ ✓✓ ✓✓ ✓✓	✓✓✓ ✓✓
10. I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this tool.	✓✓✓ ✓✓✓ ✓✓✓ ✓	✓✓✓		✓	

From these data it's been calculated the total percentage of positive and negative answers, which finally turned to be **75.71% of positive against** 12.14% being negative. The answers “Neither agree nor disagree” are taken as neutral and they're 12.14%.

Appendix 4. SUS survey results for MLM v.0, July 2022

In this testing, there were just one user who rated the tool under the threshold, which means just a 16% of user rating the tool as low usability.

User	SUS	Scale
User1	82,5	A
User 2	90	A+
User 4	87,5	A-
User 5	90	A+
User 6	55	D
Average	81	A-

Detailed summary of the answers obtained **from the “job seeker”** profile to achieve the above-mentioned results:

Regarding “My Labour Market” tool ...	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
1. I think that I would like to use this tool frequently.		✓	✓ ✓	✓ ✓	
2. I found the tool unnecessarily complex.	✓ ✓	✓ ✓	✓		
3. I thought the tool was easy to use.			✓	✓ ✓	✓ ✓
4. I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this tool.	✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓				
5. I found the various functions in this tool were well integrated.			✓	✓ ✓ ✓ ✓	
6. I thought there was too much inconsistency in this tool.	✓ ✓ ✓	✓		✓	
7. I would imagine that most people would learn to use this tool very quickly.				✓ ✓ ✓	✓ ✓
8. I found the tool very difficult to use.	✓ ✓ ✓ ✓		✓		
9. I felt very confident using the system tool.		✓		✓ ✓	✓ ✓

<p>10. I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this tool.</p>					
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Appendix 4. “Job seeker” profile questionnaire for MLM 2 gamification testing, March 2023

Grant Agreement Number: 870702

Name and surname: _____
 Evaluated system: <http://www.mylabourmarket.com/>____
 Date: _____

Introduction

Thank you for participating in this test that aims to know the degree of effectiveness, efficiency and satisfaction as well as the ease of use of My labour Market tool.

The system you are going to test is a tool which delivers personalised labour market insight to help you make better, evidence-informed decisions about your career and jobsearch. But you shall bear in mind that My Labour Market is not a job search web site.

Throughout the test we are going to ask you to perform a series of tasks that we will present to you below.

Don't worry if you make a mistake, it's normal. Keep in mind that the system is being evaluated, not you. And whether you complete the tasks successfully or not, you will be providing us with valuable information to help us improve the design of this washing machine. **So whatever you do, you will be helping us.**

It is very important that you say out loud everything that comes to your mind while you navigate through the system, the doubts that arise, the comments that occur to you, the difficulties you encounter...

1/13

Grant Agreement Number: 870702

Preliminary questionnaire

We remind you that this information is completely confidential

- What is your name?
- How old are you?
- What is your level of education?
- What is your occupation?
- How would you classify yourself in terms of your use of technology in general? Use of different devices, different types of websites or applications? (Sporadic, frequently, very often...)
- Are you used to surfing the Internet? What kind of information do you usually consult?
- Have you previously used websites or applications related to labour market information? If yes, which ones?

2/13

 Grant Agreement Number: 870702

Test scenario

You have been informed about a new online tool that provides information about the labour market.

You think it might be a good idea to get to know it, to see how you can benefit from the information it offers, according to your current job situation and your expectations. So you have decided to browse it and get first-hand information.

Let's try it!

Please **do not turn the page** until the evaluator asks you to do so.

3/13

 Grant Agreement Number: 870702

Task 1

*The first task is to get in touch with the tool, so please, open the website (<http://www.mylabourmarket.com/>) and take some time to browse through it and try to get to know what the tool offers and how to interact with it. **Please do not go through the registration process now, it will be done later.***

Detail the actions you have taken.

Let the evaluator know when you have completed the task and **do not turn the page** until the evaluator asks you to do so.

4/13

 Grant Agreement Number: 870702

Post-task 1 questionnaire

Do you think you performed the task correctly?

What is your first impression about "My Labour Market " tool?

Does the tool clearly explain the difference between being registered or not? Do you understand what services are offered to you if you are registered?

As the tool presents the information to you...Do you think it is easy to understand?

Do you miss anything? If it were possible... would you change anything?

Rate the difficulty of the task on this scale:

Very easy					Very difficult
1	2	3	4	5	

Let the evaluator know when you have completed the task and do not turn the page until the evaluator asks you to do so.

5/13

 Grant Agreement Number: 870702

Task 2

Now let's go one step further in the tool!!

Now, register yourself on the tool and log in to gain access to all services provided.

Detail the actions you have taken.

Let the evaluator know when you have completed the task and do not turn the page until the evaluator asks you to do so.

6/13

Grant Agreement Number: 870702

Post-task 2 questionnaire

Do you think you performed the task correctly?

Did you find the registration process easy and intuitive?

Did you feel comfortable with the information you were asked to fill in the registration form?

Do you miss anything? If it were possible... would you change anything?

Rate the difficulty of the task on this scale:

<small>Very easy</small>					<small>Very difficult</small>
1	2	3	4	5	

Let the evaluator know when you have completed the task and do not turn the page until the evaluator asks you to do so.

7/13

Grant Agreement Number: 870702

Task 3

According to the possibilities that the tool offers to you at the moment, try to find out what are the open vacancies available for your occupation (or the one that you prefer) in your municipality.

Once you have tried it, write your doubts or questions on this section on the platform, so that they can be answered by an expert in the job market.

Detail the actions you have taken.

Let the evaluator know when you have completed the task and do not turn the page until the evaluator asks you to do so.

8/13

Grant Agreement Number: 870702

Post-task 3 questionnaire

Do you think you performed the task correctly?

Was it easy for you to find the information? Do you think it is intuitively located?

What is your opinion about the information displayed on the map? Is it easy to understand?

What is your opinion about the information displayed on the table? Is it easy to understand? Do you find the information displayed in the different columns useful?

Is the possibility of using "more filters" clear? and is it understood what it offers?

Do you miss anything? If it were possible... would you change anything?

Rate the difficulty of the task on this scale:

Very easy	1	2	3	4	5	Very difficult
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Let the evaluator know when you have completed the task and do not turn the page until the evaluator asks you to do so.

9/13

Grant Agreement Number: 870702

Task 4

And now, the last thing...

As in the previous task you shared a question or doubt, check your workspace to see if you got an answer from the labour market expert.

Detail the actions you have taken.

Let the evaluator know when you have completed the task and do not turn the page until the evaluator asks you to do so.

10/13

Grant Agreement Number: 870702

Post-task 4 questionnaire

Do you think you performed the task correctly?

Did you find your workspace in this platform easily?

As the tool presents the information to you...Do you think it is easy to understand and to interact with?

Do you miss anything? Would you change anything?

Rate the difficulty of the task on this scale:

Very easy				Very difficult
1	2	3	4	5

Let the evaluator know when you have completed the task and do not turn the page until the evaluator asks you to do so.

11/13

Grant Agreement Number: 870702

Post-test questionnaire

We are just finishing... We will now give you a short quiz about the "My Labour Market" tool and your perception of its use. Please give us your answer in all honesty.

Does this advice service motivate you to explore deeper into the platform?

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
Agreement					

Can you explain this previous answer a bit more in detail?

Would you access the MLM platform more frequently now that you know you have this free, personalised advice service?

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
Agreement					

Can you explain this previous answer a bit more in detail?

12/13

**MY
LABOUR
MARKET**

Grant Agreement Number: 870702

HECAT
HEALTHY ECONOMICS
 CULTURAL ADAPTATION
 DIGITALISATION

How would you rate the usefulness of having this personalised support service?

	Very Low	Low	High	Very High
Usefulness				

Can you explain this previous answer a bit more in detail?

Answer

Do you have any other comments that you think are relevant?

Answer

That's it!
Thank you very much for your participation.

13/13

Appendix 5. “Councillor” profile questionnaire for MLM 2 gamification testing, March 2023

MY LABOUR MARKET

Grant Agreement Number: 870702

Name and surname: _____
 Evaluated system: <http://www.mylabourmarket.com/> _____
 Date: _____

Introduction

Thank you for participating in this test that aims to know the degree of effectiveness, efficiency and satisfaction as well as the ease of use of My labour Market tool.

The system you are about to test is a tool that provides personalised labour market information to help you make better and more informed decisions about career and job search counselling. But you should keep in mind that My Labour Market is not a job search website, but a complementary information tool to those already available in your work environment.

Throughout the test we are going to ask you to perform a series of tasks that we will present to you below.

Don't worry if you make a mistake, it's normal. Keep in mind that the system is being evaluated, not you. And whether you complete the tasks successfully or not, you will be providing us with valuable information to help us improve the design of this washing machine. **So whatever you do, you will be helping us.**

It is very important that you say out loud everything that comes to your mind while you navigate through the system, the doubts that arise, the comments that occur to you, the difficulties you encounter...

1/11

MY LABOUR MARKET

Grant Agreement Number: 870702

Preliminary questionnaire

We remind you that this information is completely confidential

- What is your name?

- How old are you?

- How long have you been working as a counsellor?

- Is there any kind of information or tool that you miss in your day-to-day work that you think could make your job easier?

- Have you previously used websites or applications (excluding the tools provided by ESS) related to labour market information? If yes, which ones?

2/11

 Grant Agreement Number: 870702

Test scenario

You have been informed about the existence of a new online tool that provides information about the labour market.

You think it might be a good idea to check it out, to see how you can benefit from the information it offers and complement the tools you already have available for counselling. So you've decided to browse it and get first-hand information.

Let's try it!

Please **do not turn the page** until the evaluator asks you to do so.

3/11

 Grant Agreement Number: 870702

Task 1

The first thing you are going to do is open the website (<http://www.mylabourmarket.com/>) and take some time to browse through it and try to get to know what the tool offers and how to interact with it.
Please do not go through the registration process now, it will be done later.

Detail the actions you have taken.

Let the evaluator know when you have **completed** the task and **do not turn the page** until the evaluator asks you to do so.

4/11

 Grant Agreement Number: 870702

Post-task 1 questionnaire

Do you think you performed the task correctly?

Did you find the registration process easy and intuitive?

Do you miss anything? If it were possible... would you change anything?

Rate the difficulty of the task on this scale:

Very easy					Very difficult
1	2	3	4	5	

Let the evaluator know when you have completed the task and do not turn the page until the evaluator asks you to do so.

5/11

 Grant Agreement Number: 870702

Task 2

Now, register yourself on the tool and log in to gain access to all services provided.

Detail the actions you have taken.

Let the evaluator know when you have completed the task and do not turn the page until the evaluator asks you to do so.

6/11

Grant Agreement Number: 870702

Post-task 2 questionnaire

Do you think you performed the task correctly?

Did you find the registration process easy and intuitive?

Did you feel comfortable with the information you were asked to fill in the registration form?

Do you miss anything? If it were possible... would you change anything?

Rate the difficulty of the task on this scale:

Very easy	1	2	3	4	5	Very difficult
-----------	---	---	---	---	---	----------------

Let the evaluator know when you have completed the task and do not turn the page until the evaluator asks you to do so.

7/11

Grant Agreement Number: 870702

Task 3

WORK SPACE

As an expert in labour marking, you are entitled to respond to questions or doubts raised by users of the tool in an area that has been set up as "doubts or questions".

Go to your personal area and check if there is any doubt raised by the user _____ . If so, try to send him/her a reply.

Detail the actions you have taken.

Let the evaluator know when you have completed the task and do not turn the page until the evaluator asks you to do so.

8/11

Grant Agreement Number: 870702

Post-task 3 questionnaire

Do you think you performed the task correctly?

Did you find it easy or intuitive to find your work space area?

Do you find the way the information is presented clearly?

Do you think it is correct that once you have answered a user's question, from that moment on, all of this user's queries are assigned to you?

Do you miss anything? Would you change anything?

Rate the difficulty of the task on this scale:

Very easy					Very difficult
1	2	3	4	5	

Let the evaluator know when you have completed the task and do not turn the page until the evaluator asks you to do so.

9/11

Grant Agreement Number: 870702

Post-test questionnaire

We are just finishing... We will now give you a short quiz about the "My Labour Market" tool and your perception of its use. Please give us your answer in all honesty.

I believe that "My Labour Market" tool will be useful for me to complement the tools I already have available to offer the counselling service.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly
Agreement					

Can you explain this previous answer a bit more in detail?

I consider appropriate and useful to be able to give my expert support through the online service offered by this platform.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly
Agreement					

Can you explain this previous answer a bit more in detail?

10/11

Grant Agreement Number: 870702

Do you have any other comments?

Answer

That's it!
Thank you very much for your participation.

11/11

